

APPENDIX B: UNIT ROOT TESTS

A1 Augmented Dickey-Fuller Test

Null Hypothesis: LRGDP has a unit root

Exogenous: Constant

Lag Length: 1 (Automatic - based on SIC, maxlag=8)

	t-Statistic	Prob.*
Augmented Dickey-Fuller test statistic	-0.723543	0.8270
Test critical values:		
1% level	-3.646342	
5% level	-2.954021	
10% level	-2.615817	

*MacKinnon (1996) one-sided p-values.

Augmented Dickey-Fuller Test Equation

Dependent Variable: D(LRGDP)

Method: Least Squares

Date: 04/03/26 Time: 17:26

Sample (adjusted): 1992 2024

Included observations: 33 after adjustments

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
LRGDP(-1)	-0.007860	0.010864	-0.723543	0.4750
D(LRGDP(-1))	0.573774	0.145557	3.941917	0.0004
C	0.100901	0.115503	0.873582	0.3893
R-squared	0.345860	Mean dependent var		0.039491
Adjusted R-squared	0.302251	S.D. dependent var		0.035288
S.E. of regression	0.029476	Akaike info criterion		-4.123942
Sum squared resid	0.026066	Schwarz criterion		-3.987896
Log likelihood	71.04505	Hannan-Quinn criter.		-4.078167
F-statistic	7.930882	Durbin-Watson stat		2.185931
Prob(F-statistic)	0.001718			

Null Hypothesis: D(LRGDP) has a unit root

Exogenous: Constant

Lag Length: 0 (Automatic - based on SIC, maxlag=8)

	t-Statistic	Prob.*
Augmented Dickey-Fuller test statistic	-2.982110	0.0471
Test critical values:		
1% level	-3.646342	
5% level	-2.954021	
10% level	-2.615817	

*MacKinnon (1996) one-sided p-values.

Augmented Dickey-Fuller Test Equation

Dependent Variable: D(LRGDP,2)

Method: Least Squares

Date: 04/03/26 Time: 17:27

Sample (adjusted): 1992 2024
 Included observations: 33 after adjustments

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
D(LRGDP(-1))	-0.430383	0.144322	-2.982110	0.0055
C	0.017511	0.007546	2.320664	0.0271
R-squared	0.222921	Mean dependent var		0.000904
Adjusted R-squared	0.197854	S.D. dependent var		0.032658
S.E. of regression	0.029249	Akaike info criterion		-4.167249
Sum squared resid	0.026521	Schwarz criterion		-4.076551
Log likelihood	70.75960	Hannan-Quinn criter.		-4.136732
F-statistic	8.892981	Durbin-Watson stat		2.154168
Prob(F-statistic)	0.005534			

Null Hypothesis: LCAPEX has a unit root
 Exogenous: Constant
 Lag Length: 1 (Automatic - based on SIC, maxlag=8)

	t-Statistic	Prob.*
Augmented Dickey-Fuller test statistic	-1.725622	0.4095
Test critical values:		
1% level	-3.646342	
5% level	-2.954021	
10% level	-2.615817	

*MacKinnon (1996) one-sided p-values.

Augmented Dickey-Fuller Test Equation
 Dependent Variable: D(LCAPEX)
 Method: Least Squares
 Date: 04/03/26 Time: 17:27
 Sample (adjusted): 1992 2024
 Included observations: 33 after adjustments

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
LCAPEX(-1)	-0.077560	0.044946	-1.725622	0.0947
D(LCAPEX(-1))	-0.207850	0.170644	-1.218036	0.2327
C	0.673809	0.287592	2.342930	0.0260
R-squared	0.127411	Mean dependent var		0.156716
Adjusted R-squared	0.069238	S.D. dependent var		0.323938
S.E. of regression	0.312522	Akaike info criterion		0.598225
Sum squared resid	2.930103	Schwarz criterion		0.734272
Log likelihood	-6.870719	Hannan-Quinn criter.		0.644001
F-statistic	2.190220	Durbin-Watson stat		1.940515
Prob(F-statistic)	0.129464			

Null Hypothesis: D(LCAPEX) has a unit root
 Exogenous: Constant
 Lag Length: 0 (Automatic - based on SIC, maxlag=8)

	t-Statistic	Prob.*
Augmented Dickey-Fuller test statistic	-6.831105	0.0000
Test critical values:		
1% level	-3.646342	
5% level	-2.954021	
10% level	-2.615817	

*MacKinnon (1996) one-sided p-values.

Augmented Dickey-Fuller Test Equation
 Dependent Variable: D(LCAPEX,2)
 Method: Least Squares
 Date: 04/03/26 Time: 17:28
 Sample (adjusted): 1992 2024
 Included observations: 33 after adjustments

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
D(LCAPEX(-1))	-1.202061	0.175969	-6.831105	0.0000
C	0.188731	0.062657	3.012135	0.0051
R-squared	0.600845	Mean dependent var		-0.001729
Adjusted R-squared	0.587969	S.D. dependent var		0.502164
S.E. of regression	0.322337	Akaike info criterion		0.632256
Sum squared resid	3.220943	Schwarz criterion		0.722953
Log likelihood	-8.432219	Hannan-Quinn criter.		0.662773
F-statistic	46.66399	Durbin-Watson stat		1.926340
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

Null Hypothesis: LRECEX has a unit root
 Exogenous: Constant
 Lag Length: 0 (Automatic - based on SIC, maxlag=8)

	t-Statistic	Prob.*
Augmented Dickey-Fuller test statistic	-1.225744	0.6518
Test critical values:		
1% level	-3.639407	
5% level	-2.951125	
10% level	-2.614300	

*MacKinnon (1996) one-sided p-values.

Augmented Dickey-Fuller Test Equation
 Dependent Variable: D(LRECEX)
 Method: Least Squares
 Date: 04/03/26 Time: 17:28
 Sample (adjusted): 1991 2024
 Included observations: 34 after adjustments

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
LRECEX(-1)	-0.029418	0.024000	-1.225744	0.2292
C	0.390533	0.172237	2.267419	0.0303

R-squared	0.044846	Mean dependent var	0.185575
Adjusted R-squared	0.014997	S.D. dependent var	0.242670
S.E. of regression	0.240843	Akaike info criterion	0.047679
Sum squared resid	1.856170	Schwarz criterion	0.137465
Log likelihood	1.189456	Hannan-Quinn criter.	0.078299
F-statistic	1.502447	Durbin-Watson stat	2.723759
Prob(F-statistic)	0.229240		

Null Hypothesis: D(LRECEX) has a unit root
Exogenous: Constant
Lag Length: 0 (Automatic - based on SIC, maxlag=8)

	t-Statistic	Prob.*
Augmented Dickey-Fuller test statistic	-8.035220	0.0000
Test critical values:		
1% level	-3.646342	
5% level	-2.954021	
10% level	-2.615817	

*MacKinnon (1996) one-sided p-values.

Augmented Dickey-Fuller Test Equation
Dependent Variable: D(LRECEX,2)
Method: Least Squares
Date: 04/03/26 Time: 17:29
Sample (adjusted): 1992 2024
Included observations: 33 after adjustments

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
D(LRECEX(-1))	-1.352359	0.168304	-8.035220	0.0000
C	0.253377	0.050779	4.989771	0.0000
R-squared	0.675613	Mean dependent var	0.008413	
Adjusted R-squared	0.665149	S.D. dependent var	0.403141	
S.E. of regression	0.233283	Akaike info criterion	-0.014436	
Sum squared resid	1.687051	Schwarz criterion	0.076261	
Log likelihood	2.238195	Hannan-Quinn criter.	0.016081	
F-statistic	64.56477	Durbin-Watson stat	1.947273	
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

LOILREV AT LVL

Null Hypothesis: LOILREV has a unit root
Exogenous: Constant
Lag Length: 0 (Automatic - based on SIC, maxlag=8)

	t-Statistic	Prob.*
Augmented Dickey-Fuller test statistic	-1.917795	0.3205

Test critical values:	1% level	-3.639407
	5% level	-2.951125
	10% level	-2.614300

*MacKinnon (1996) one-sided p-values.

Augmented Dickey-Fuller Test Equation
 Dependent Variable: D(LOILREV)
 Method: Least Squares
 Date: 04/03/26 Time: 17:29
 Sample (adjusted): 1991 2024
 Included observations: 34 after adjustments

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
LOILREV(-1)	-0.085736	0.044705	-1.917795	0.0641
C	0.791939	0.339931	2.329703	0.0263
R-squared	0.103087	Mean dependent var		0.151843
Adjusted R-squared	0.075059	S.D. dependent var		0.390722
S.E. of regression	0.375773	Akaike info criterion		0.937357
Sum squared resid	4.518560	Schwarz criterion		1.027143
Log likelihood	-13.93507	Hannan-Quinn criter.		0.967976
F-statistic	3.677936	Durbin-Watson stat		1.904623
Prob(F-statistic)	0.064099			

LOILREV AT FIRST DIFF

Null Hypothesis: D(LOILREV) has a unit root
 Exogenous: Constant
 Lag Length: 0 (Automatic - based on SIC, maxlag=8)

	t-Statistic	Prob.*
Augmented Dickey-Fuller test statistic	-5.129094	0.0002
Test critical values:		
	1% level	-3.646342
	5% level	-2.954021
	10% level	-2.615817

*MacKinnon (1996) one-sided p-values.

Augmented Dickey-Fuller Test Equation
 Dependent Variable: D(LOILREV,2)
 Method: Least Squares
 Date: 04/03/26 Time: 17:30
 Sample (adjusted): 1992 2024
 Included observations: 33 after adjustments

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
D(LOILREV(-1))	-0.962330	0.187622	-5.129094	0.0000
C	0.147226	0.074394	1.979001	0.0568

R-squared	0.459060	Mean dependent var	0.019886
Adjusted R-squared	0.441610	S.D. dependent var	0.539121
S.E. of regression	0.402861	Akaike info criterion	1.078242
Sum squared resid	5.031208	Schwarz criterion	1.168939
Log likelihood	-15.79099	Hannan-Quinn criter.	1.108759
F-statistic	26.30761	Durbin-Watson stat	1.838512
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000015		

LNONOILREV AT LVL

Null Hypothesis: LNONOILREV has a unit root
 Exogenous: Constant
 Lag Length: 0 (Automatic - based on SIC, maxlag=8)

	t-Statistic	Prob.*
Augmented Dickey-Fuller test statistic	-0.210376	0.9277
Test critical values:		
1% level	-3.639407	
5% level	-2.951125	
10% level	-2.614300	

*MacKinnon (1996) one-sided p-values.

Augmented Dickey-Fuller Test Equation
 Dependent Variable: D(LNONOILREV)
 Method: Least Squares
 Date: 04/03/26 Time: 17:31
 Sample (adjusted): 1991 2024
 Included observations: 34 after adjustments

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
LNONOILREV(-1)	-0.005935	0.028212	-0.210376	0.8347
C	0.245846	0.192342	1.278173	0.2104
R-squared	0.001381	Mean dependent var		0.206852
Adjusted R-squared	-0.029826	S.D. dependent var		0.295215
S.E. of regression	0.299586	Akaike info criterion		0.484189
Sum squared resid	2.872049	Schwarz criterion		0.573975
Log likelihood	-6.231216	Hannan-Quinn criter.		0.514809
F-statistic	0.044258	Durbin-Watson stat		2.121413
Prob(F-statistic)	0.834708			

LNONOILREV AT FIRST

Null Hypothesis: D(LNONOILREV) has a unit root
 Exogenous: Constant
 Lag Length: 0 (Automatic - based on SIC, maxlag=8)

t-Statistic Prob.*

Augmented Dickey-Fuller test statistic		-6.788981	0.0000
Test critical values:	1% level	-3.646342	
	5% level	-2.954021	
	10% level	-2.615817	

*MacKinnon (1996) one-sided p-values.

Augmented Dickey-Fuller Test Equation
 Dependent Variable: D(LNONOILREV,2)
 Method: Least Squares
 Date: 04/03/26 Time: 17:31
 Sample (adjusted): 1992 2024
 Included observations: 33 after adjustments

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
D(LNONOILREV(-1))	-1.198209	0.176493	-6.788981	0.0000
C	0.261514	0.059247	4.413990	0.0001
R-squared	0.597874	Mean dependent var		0.034560
Adjusted R-squared	0.584902	S.D. dependent var		0.436131
S.E. of regression	0.280991	Akaike info criterion		0.357705
Sum squared resid	2.447637	Schwarz criterion		0.448402
Log likelihood	-3.902127	Hannan-Quinn criter.		0.388222
F-statistic	46.09027	Durbin-Watson stat		1.768245
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

A2 Phillips-Perron Test

Null Hypothesis: LRGDP has a unit root
 Exogenous: Constant
 Bandwidth: 4 (Newey-West automatic) using Bartlett kernel

	Adj. t-Stat	Prob.*
Phillips-Perron test statistic	-0.363549	0.9044
Test critical values:		
	1% level	-3.639407
	5% level	-2.951125
	10% level	-2.614300

*MacKinnon (1996) one-sided p-values.

Residual variance (no correction)	0.001207
HAC corrected variance (Bartlett kernel)	0.003388

Phillips-Perron Test Equation
 Dependent Variable: D(LRGDP)
 Method: Least Squares
 Date: 04/03/26 Time: 17:32
 Sample (adjusted): 1991 2024
 Included observations: 34 after adjustments

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
LRGDP(-1)	-0.002909	0.012830	-0.226708	0.8221
C	0.069296	0.136265	0.508536	0.6146
R-squared	0.001604	Mean dependent var		0.038435
Adjusted R-squared	-0.029596	S.D. dependent var		0.035291
S.E. of regression	0.035809	Akaike info criterion		-3.764201
Sum squared resid	0.041034	Schwarz criterion		-3.674415
Log likelihood	65.99142	Hannan-Quinn criter.		-3.733581
F-statistic	0.051396	Durbin-Watson stat		0.830058
Prob(F-statistic)	0.822093			

Null Hypothesis: D(LRGDP) has a unit root
Exogenous: Constant
Bandwidth: 4 (Newey-West automatic) using Bartlett kernel

	Adj. t-Stat	Prob.*
Phillips-Perron test statistic	-2.958125	0.0496
Test critical values:		
1% level	-3.646342	
5% level	-2.954021	
10% level	-2.615817	

*MacKinnon (1996) one-sided p-values.

Residual variance (no correction)	0.000804
HAC corrected variance (Bartlett kernel)	0.000780

Phillips-Perron Test Equation
Dependent Variable: D(LRGDP,2)
Method: Least Squares
Date: 04/03/26 Time: 17:33
Sample (adjusted): 1992 2024
Included observations: 33 after adjustments

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
D(LRGDP(-1))	-0.430383	0.144322	-2.982110	0.0055
C	0.017511	0.007546	2.320664	0.0271
R-squared	0.222921	Mean dependent var		0.000904
Adjusted R-squared	0.197854	S.D. dependent var		0.032658
S.E. of regression	0.029249	Akaike info criterion		-4.167249
Sum squared resid	0.026521	Schwarz criterion		-4.076551
Log likelihood	70.75960	Hannan-Quinn criter.		-4.136732
F-statistic	8.892981	Durbin-Watson stat		2.154168
Prob(F-statistic)	0.005534			

Null Hypothesis: LCAPEX has a unit root
Exogenous: Constant

Bandwidth: 1 (Newey-West automatic) using Bartlett kernel

	Adj. t-Stat	Prob.*
Phillips-Perron test statistic	-1.611969	0.4657
Test critical values:		
1% level	-3.639407	
5% level	-2.951125	
10% level	-2.614300	

*MacKinnon (1996) one-sided p-values.

Residual variance (no correction)	0.091676
HAC corrected variance (Bartlett kernel)	0.071484

Phillips-Perron Test Equation
 Dependent Variable: D(LCAPEX)
 Method: Least Squares
 Date: 04/03/26 Time: 17:33
 Sample (adjusted): 1991 2024
 Included observations: 34 after adjustments

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
LCAPEX(-1)	-0.064759	0.041170	-1.572970	0.1256
C	0.555354	0.258883	2.145191	0.0396
R-squared	0.071771	Mean dependent var		0.156937
Adjusted R-squared	0.042763	S.D. dependent var		0.318994
S.E. of regression	0.312099	Akaike info criterion		0.566032
Sum squared resid	3.116991	Schwarz criterion		0.655818
Log likelihood	-7.622538	Hannan-Quinn criter.		0.596651
F-statistic	2.474236	Durbin-Watson stat		2.426529
Prob(F-statistic)	0.125562			

Null Hypothesis: D(LCAPEX) has a unit root
 Exogenous: Constant
 Bandwidth: 2 (Newey-West automatic) using Bartlett kernel

	Adj. t-Stat	Prob.*
Phillips-Perron test statistic	-6.765173	0.0000
Test critical values:		
1% level	-3.646342	
5% level	-2.954021	
10% level	-2.615817	

*MacKinnon (1996) one-sided p-values.

Residual variance (no correction)	0.097604
HAC corrected variance (Bartlett kernel)	0.111786

Phillips-Perron Test Equation
 Dependent Variable: D(LCAPEX,2)
 Method: Least Squares
 Date: 04/03/26 Time: 17:34
 Sample (adjusted): 1992 2024
 Included observations: 33 after adjustments

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
D(LCAPEX(-1))	-1.202061	0.175969	-6.831105	0.0000
C	0.188731	0.062657	3.012135	0.0051
R-squared	0.600845	Mean dependent var		-0.001729
Adjusted R-squared	0.587969	S.D. dependent var		0.502164
S.E. of regression	0.322337	Akaike info criterion		0.632256
Sum squared resid	3.220943	Schwarz criterion		0.722953
Log likelihood	-8.432219	Hannan-Quinn criter.		0.662773
F-statistic	46.66399	Durbin-Watson stat		1.926340
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

Null Hypothesis: LRECEX has a unit root
 Exogenous: Constant
 Bandwidth: 12 (Newey-West automatic) using Bartlett kernel

	Adj. t-Stat	Prob.*
Phillips-Perron test statistic	-1.810594	0.3692
Test critical values:		
1% level	-3.639407	
5% level	-2.951125	
10% level	-2.614300	

*MacKinnon (1996) one-sided p-values.

Residual variance (no correction)	0.054593
HAC corrected variance (Bartlett kernel)	0.014578

Phillips-Perron Test Equation
 Dependent Variable: D(LRECEX)
 Method: Least Squares
 Date: 04/03/26 Time: 17:34
 Sample (adjusted): 1991 2024
 Included observations: 34 after adjustments

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
LRECEX(-1)	-0.029418	0.024000	-1.225744	0.2292
C	0.390533	0.172237	2.267419	0.0303
R-squared	0.044846	Mean dependent var		0.185575
Adjusted R-squared	0.014997	S.D. dependent var		0.242670
S.E. of regression	0.240843	Akaike info criterion		0.047679
Sum squared resid	1.856170	Schwarz criterion		0.137465
Log likelihood	1.189456	Hannan-Quinn criter.		0.078299
F-statistic	1.502447	Durbin-Watson stat		2.723759

Prob(F-statistic) 0.229240

Null Hypothesis: D(LRECEX) has a unit root
Exogenous: Constant
Bandwidth: 1 (Newey-West automatic) using Bartlett kernel

		Adj. t-Stat	Prob.*
Phillips-Perron test statistic		-8.015473	0.0000
Test critical values:	1% level	-3.646342	
	5% level	-2.954021	
	10% level	-2.615817	

*MacKinnon (1996) one-sided p-values.

Residual variance (no correction)	0.051123
HAC corrected variance (Bartlett kernel)	0.051899

Phillips-Perron Test Equation
Dependent Variable: D(LRECEX,2)
Method: Least Squares
Date: 04/03/26 Time: 17:35
Sample (adjusted): 1992 2024
Included observations: 33 after adjustments

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
D(LRECEX(-1))	-1.352359	0.168304	-8.035220	0.0000
C	0.253377	0.050779	4.989771	0.0000
R-squared	0.675613	Mean dependent var		0.008413
Adjusted R-squared	0.665149	S.D. dependent var		0.403141
S.E. of regression	0.233283	Akaike info criterion		-0.014436
Sum squared resid	1.687051	Schwarz criterion		0.076261
Log likelihood	2.238195	Hannan-Quinn criter.		0.016081
F-statistic	64.56477	Durbin-Watson stat		1.947273
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

Null Hypothesis: LOILREV has a unit root
Exogenous: Constant
Bandwidth: 16 (Newey-West automatic) using Bartlett kernel

	Adj. t-Stat	Prob.*
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Phillips-Perron test statistic		-2.818839	0.0662
Test critical values:	1% level	-3.639407	
	5% level	-2.951125	
	10% level	-2.614300	

*MacKinnon (1996) one-sided p-values.

Residual variance (no correction)	0.132899
HAC corrected variance (Bartlett kernel)	0.030459

Phillips-Perron Test Equation
 Dependent Variable: D(LOILREV)
 Method: Least Squares
 Date: 04/03/26 Time: 17:35
 Sample (adjusted): 1991 2024
 Included observations: 34 after adjustments

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
LOILREV(-1)	-0.085736	0.044705	-1.917795	0.0641
C	0.791939	0.339931	2.329703	0.0263
R-squared	0.103087	Mean dependent var		0.151843
Adjusted R-squared	0.075059	S.D. dependent var		0.390722
S.E. of regression	0.375773	Akaike info criterion		0.937357
Sum squared resid	4.518560	Schwarz criterion		1.027143
Log likelihood	-13.93507	Hannan-Quinn criter.		0.967976
F-statistic	3.677936	Durbin-Watson stat		1.904623
Prob(F-statistic)	0.064099			

Null Hypothesis: D(LOILREV) has a unit root
 Exogenous: Constant
 Bandwidth: 6 (Newey-West automatic) using Bartlett kernel

	Adj. t-Stat	Prob.*
Phillips-Perron test statistic	-5.063434	0.0002
Test critical values:		
	1% level	-3.646342
	5% level	-2.954021
	10% level	-2.615817

*MacKinnon (1996) one-sided p-values.

Residual variance (no correction)	0.152461
HAC corrected variance (Bartlett kernel)	0.121857

Phillips-Perron Test Equation
 Dependent Variable: D(LOILREV,2)
 Method: Least Squares

Date: 04/05/26 Time: 13:50
Sample (adjusted): 1992 2024
Included observations: 33 after adjustments

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
D(LOILREV(-1))	-0.962330	0.187622	-5.129094	0.0000
C	0.147226	0.074394	1.979001	0.0568
R-squared	0.459060	Mean dependent var		0.019886
Adjusted R-squared	0.441610	S.D. dependent var		0.539121
S.E. of regression	0.402861	Akaike info criterion		1.078242
Sum squared resid	5.031208	Schwarz criterion		1.168939
Log likelihood	-15.79099	Hannan-Quinn criter.		1.108759
F-statistic	26.30761	Durbin-Watson stat		1.838512
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000015			

Null Hypothesis: LNONOILREV has a unit root
Exogenous: Constant
Bandwidth: 3 (Newey-West automatic) using Bartlett kernel

	Adj. t-Stat	Prob.*
Phillips-Perron test statistic	-0.141269	0.9367
Test critical values:		
1% level	-3.639407	
5% level	-2.951125	
10% level	-2.614300	

*MacKinnon (1996) one-sided p-values.

Residual variance (no correction)	0.084472
HAC corrected variance (Bartlett kernel)	0.069550

Phillips-Perron Test Equation
Dependent Variable: D(LNONOILREV)
Method: Least Squares
Date: 04/03/26 Time: 17:36
Sample (adjusted): 1991 2024
Included observations: 34 after adjustments

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
LNONOILREV(-1)	-0.005935	0.028212	-0.210376	0.8347
C	0.245846	0.192342	1.278173	0.2104
R-squared	0.001381	Mean dependent var		0.206852
Adjusted R-squared	-0.029826	S.D. dependent var		0.295215
S.E. of regression	0.299586	Akaike info criterion		0.484189
Sum squared resid	2.872049	Schwarz criterion		0.573975
Log likelihood	-6.231216	Hannan-Quinn criter.		0.514809
F-statistic	0.044258	Durbin-Watson stat		2.121413
Prob(F-statistic)	0.834708			

Null Hypothesis: D(LNONOILREV) has a unit root
 Exogenous: Constant
 Bandwidth: 2 (Newey-West automatic) using Bartlett kernel

	Adj. t-Stat	Prob.*
Phillips-Perron test statistic	-6.726127	0.0000
Test critical values:		
1% level	-3.646342	
5% level	-2.954021	
10% level	-2.615817	

*MacKinnon (1996) one-sided p-values.

Residual variance (no correction)	0.074171
HAC corrected variance (Bartlett kernel)	0.085153

Phillips-Perron Test Equation
 Dependent Variable: D(LNONOILREV,2)
 Method: Least Squares
 Date: 04/03/26 Time: 17:37
 Sample (adjusted): 1992 2024
 Included observations: 33 after adjustments

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
D(LNONOILREV(-1))	-1.198209	0.176493	-6.788981	0.0000
C	0.261514	0.059247	4.413990	0.0001
R-squared	0.597874	Mean dependent var		0.034560
Adjusted R-squared	0.584902	S.D. dependent var		0.436131
S.E. of regression	0.280991	Akaike info criterion		0.357705
Sum squared resid	2.447637	Schwarz criterion		0.448402
Log likelihood	-3.902127	Hannan-Quinn criter.		0.388222
F-statistic	46.09027	Durbin-Watson stat		1.768245
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			